

BRILL

Stem, prefix or prefixoid?

Resolving the status of pale-, παλ-, and παλο- in Standard Modern Greek

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Abstract

In this study, I parameterize the five tests proposed by Stevens (2005) for characterizing an element as an affixoid and formulate ten criteria for prefixation. Using these criteria, I analyze the morphological status of the initial components of Modern Greek words beginning with *pale-* and *παλο-*. Contrary to Giannouloupoulou's (1999) analysis of *paleo-* as a “confix” and *παλο-* as a “stem”, I argue that *pale-* is a stem that has two allomorphic realizations: *pale-παλ-*. *pale-* is marked as [+learnèd] and *παλ-* as [-learnèd]. While *παλο-* historically derives from *pale-*, it has acquired a distinct morphological status and should now be considered a prefixoid. The ten criteria I present could serve as a model for determining the morphological status of initial elements in other Greek morphological structures and potentially in other languages where this status is ambiguous. Finally, I propose that prefixation in Greek differs from that in word-based languages. In Greek, prefixation is not a case of morphologization; rather, prefixes originate in and remain confined to the morphological domain.

Keywords

pale – *παλο* – prefixoids – prefixization criteria – grammaticalization – Standard Modern Greek

1 An identity problem

The first constituent in the structures in (iii), (2ii) and (iii), (2iii) respectively, derives etymologically from the adjective *παλαιός* *pale'os* 'old'. If we compare the examples given in (1) and (2), we notice that the first constituent in (iii) and (2ii) seems to differ in meaning from the first constituent in (iii) and (2iii). In (iii) and (2ii), the first constituent means 'one that existed for a long time/existed in the past', while in (iii) and (2iii), it accords a negative connotation to the second component.¹

- (1) i. *vivliopo'lio* 'bookstore'
 ii. *paleovivliopo'lio* 'secondhand bookstore'
 iii. *παλoνvivliopo'lio* 'shabby bookstore'
- (2) i. *komuni'stis* 'communist'
 ii. *paleokomuni'stis* 'old-fashioned communist'
 iii. *παλoκομuni'stis* 'damn communist'

The Dictionary of Standard Modern Greek (Manolis Triantafyllidis Foundation) considers the first constituent between the structures in (iii) and (iii) and, respectively, in (2ii) and (2iii), to differ mainly in register, considering the first one to be [+learnèd] and treating the second as [-learnèd] and sometimes the oral alternative of the first. Moreover, this dictionary implies that this morphologically unique element has the grammatical status of a stem² since all examples cited both in (iii–iii) and (2ii–iii) are considered to have been created by the morphological process of compounding.³

However, Giannoulopoulou (1999) examines structures like these and concludes that *pale-* and *παλo-* are actually two morphologically distinct elements. *παλo-* is analyzed as a stem (1999: 164) and, even when it participates in struc-

1 When it is a free word, its primary meaning is 'old'. As *pale'os* (a), it is realized in [+learnèd] contexts and as *παλoς* (b) in [-learnèd] contexts.

(a) *pale'a 'pragmata* 'old things'

(b) *παλo'ka 'pragmata* 'old things'

Furthermore, without distinguishing between the two realizations (namely, *pale'os* and *παλoς*), Guardiano & Stavrou (2019: 14–18), to some extent following Kolliakou (2004), discuss the syntactic distribution of the adjectives as a free word in SMG. They examine definiteness, considering the presence or absence of the article and the adjective's syntactic position.

2 On the notion of *stem* in Greek, see Marinis (2024a).

3 According to the dictionary, *παλo-* is structurally always the "first constituent in compound nouns [*α' συνθετικό σε σύνθετα ονόματα*]".

tures such as those in (2iii),⁴ it is still characterized as a “free morpheme [ελεύθερο μόρφημα]” (1999: 200). In contrast to *παλο-*, Giannouloupoulou analyzes *paleo-* not as a free morpheme but as a “confix [σύνφυμα]”⁵ (1999: 139, 164).

Although Giannouloupoulou’s claim about these two morphologically distinct elements seems more convincing than the one implied by the Dictionary of the Manolis Triantafyllidis Foundation, her analysis, too, remains problematic, for several reasons.

First, turning attention to *paleo*:

- Given that the stem of the adjective *paleos* is *pale-* (note: *pale(os)-M—pale(a)-F—pale(o)-N*), we have no reason to think that the element in examples (iii) and (2ii) is **paleo-*. Instead, the element contains the stem of the adjective, namely *pale-*, and the *-o-* follows as a simple compositional marker. *paleo-* is thus aligned with the more general scheme of compound structuring, [stem/word + *o* + stem/word], which has been proposed for Modern Greek by Ralli (2013, 2022). It is schematically captured in examples (3i) and (3ii).

- (3) i. *spanak- -o- -pita*
 spinach pie
 ‘spinach pie’
- ii. *pale- -o- -vivliopolio*⁶
 old bookstore
 ‘secondhand bookstore’

- Moreover, this same form, without the *-o-*, is preserved when the *pale-* element is to the right of a structure, as in (4). The hypothesis of the existence of two distinct morphological entities, in order to interpret structures like those in (iii), (2ii), and (4), respectively, would lack both economy and clear

4 She gives the example *παλοδεξι'os* ‘old conservative bastard’.

5 Defining the way she uses the term, Giannouloupoulou (1999: 13) notes that «confixes ... are considered to belong to the intermediate zones between compounding and derivation [Τα συμφύματα ... θεωρούνται ότι ανήκουν στις ενδιάμεσες ζώνες μεταξύ της σύνθεσης και της παραγωγής]».

6 The second constituent of the compound (3ii) is a complete word that is further segmentable. This word is itself a compound consisting of the following constituents: the stem *vivli-* ‘book’, the compositional marker *-o-*, the stem *-pol-* ‘sell’, a phonologically non-realized derivational morpheme indicating ‘person acting’, the derivational morpheme *-i-* ‘the space within which the work takes place’, and the inflectional suffix *-o* carrying the information [+neuter], [+nominative], [+singular].

motivation. This is because, in the examples (iii) and (2ii) on the one hand, and in example (4) on the other, the structure and meaning align completely.

- (4) i. *pam*⁷- *-bale*⁸- *-os*⁹
 old M.NOM.SG¹⁰
 ‘very old-NOM.SG.M’
 ii. *pam*- *-bale*- *-a/i*
 old F.NOM.SG
 ‘very old-NOM.SG.F’
 iii. *pam*- *-bale*- *-o*
 old N.NOM.SG
 ‘very old-NOM.SG.N’

– In terms of form, *pale-* is identical to the stem of the adjective *paleos*-M—*palea*-F—*paleo*-N ‘old’. Also, the meaning of *pale-* in the structures in which it participates is identical to the original meaning of the stem of the *paleos*-M—*palea*-F—*paleo*-N ‘old’ (see [1ii] and [2ii]).

Similarly, the analysis proposed for the element *paλo-* also seems problematic, since:

- In neither example (1iii) nor (2iii) does the element *paλo-* behave as the first constituent of a compound.
- In the same examples, only *paλo-* conveys a negative connotation in the second component, distinguishing it from the adjective *paleos/palos* ‘old’.
- In contrast, whenever *paλ(o)-* is on the right of a structure, both its meaning and its form remain the same as in the stem of the adjective *paleos/palos* ‘old’ (5).

7 The constituent *pan-* that is realized here as *pam-* for phonological reasons; it assimilates to the feature [+bilabial] from the next [+bilabial] segment. *pan-* historically originates from the Ancient Greek adjective *πάς, πάσα, πάν*. Today it acts as the first component in morphological structures, where it either intensifies the property expressed by the second component or encompasses all the elements implied by the second component.

8 Here, *pale* is realized as *bale* because the initial consonant assimilates to the [+voiced] feature from the preceding segment.

9 For the nominal inflection sets of inflectional suffixes that exist in SMG, see Ralli (2022). Additionally, see Marinis (2024b) for argumentation on their elimination through expanded case syncretism.

10 In glossing, I follow the Leipzig glossing rules and their list of standard abbreviations, including M for masculine, F for feminine, N for neuter, NOM for nominative, SG for singular, and PL for plural.

- (5) i. *para-* *-παλ-* *-i*
 old -M.NOM.PL
 'too old-NOM.PL.M'

I undertake here an in-depth analysis of the structural, semantic, and phonological behavior of Greek formations whose first component is derived from *παλαιός* *pale'os* 'old'. Through this analysis, the following questions are addressed:

1. In the mind of a native speaker of *Standard Modern Greek* (hereinafter SMG), are there synchronically one, two, or three morphemes derived from *παλαιός* *pale'os* 'old'?
2. If the answer to question 1 is "two" or "three", what is the phonological realization of each morpheme?
3. What is the status of each morpheme whose phonological realization is determined in question 2? Is it a stem, a prefix, or a prefixoid?
4. Also, if Giannouloupoulou's analysis is incorrect, what alternative criteria can be used to determine whether an element has the status of a prefixoid?

The presentation is structured as follows: In Section 2, I summarize the basic structural, phonological, and semantic features that we would theoretically expect a stem, a prefix, and a prefixoid to exhibit. In Section 3, using the ten specific criteria I set up in Section 2, I examine Greek words with *pale-* and *παλο-* as their first constituent to determine the synchronic status of these elements. In Section 4, I discuss the implications of the preceding analysis defining the synchronic status of *pale-* and *παλο-*. Finally, in Section 5, I discuss the broader theoretical implications of my proposed criteria for examining the process by which a form becomes a prefix, what I call here *prefixization* (following Ralli 2018, van Goethem 2008).

2 When the stem aspires to become a prefix

Language is a living organism that constantly undergoes processes of change, triggered by either causes internal to the system or by paralinguistic ones (see, for example, Marinis 2020a: 57–82, 161–175). One category of change, grammaticalization, is defined by Meillet (1912) as the process by which lexical words gradually lose their independence and semantic richness to develop a more grammatical status of function. According to Kuryłowicz (1965: 69), the phenomenon can extend to an already grammatical element that acquires an even more grammatical character. Indeed, according to Joseph (2014; 2021), there

are cases of grammaticalization which could be argued to consist of several successive grammaticalizations,¹¹ with the development of the Modern Greek future being a prime example. We could argue that such changes meet the criteria of the grammaticalization definitions of both Meillet (1912) and Kuryłowicz (1965).

In such a path of grammaticalization, prefixoids may be viewed as elements that are morphologically in flux (Amiot 2005; Amiot and Dugas 2020; Booiĵ 2005; Efthymiou et al. 2015; Faust 2021; Joseph 2003; Masini and Micheli 2020; Ralli 2020; Stevens 2005; ten Hacken 2000; van Goethem 2008); they seem to be passing from the category of stem to that of prefix. Therefore, they are, at present, neither stems nor prefixes, but rather elements which, having once been stems, are now tending toward becoming prefixes, without any guarantee as to when—or even whether—that transition will be completed.

Before discussing those bases on which we could classify a morpheme as a prefix, let us describe the fundamental structural distinctions between stems and prefixes. Indeed, stems and prefixes differ significantly in several features:

1. Stems generally carry a specific lexical meaning, unlike prefixes, whose meaning is usually abstract.
2. Stems belong to a specific grammatical category, marked in the Lexicon as nouns, adjectives, verbs, adverbs, etc. In contrast, prefixes do not have a grammatical category.
3. Unlike stems, which show comparatively greater autonomy, prefixes are usually absolutely bound to the base of the morphological formation and are generally not releasable.
4. Unlike stems, which, when combined with another stem, can be placed in any position of the structure depending on their role (e.g., if they are the head of the structure), prefixes are always bound to the structure's left.

Since prefixoids are, by definition, in the process of changing, moving from stems to prefixes, one has to consider how they may be defined. Their features may not coincide entirely with those of either stems or prefixes.

Stevens (2005), building on the observations of the earlier German-language literature of the 1970s and 1980s, and parameterizing Stevens (2000), proposes five criteria for classifying an element as an affixoid:¹²

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- 11 In the case of the Greek future, Joseph (2014) ultimately argues that the developments are best viewed as involving just one grammaticalization step, the movement from the lexical verb meaning 'want' to a grammatical marker signaling futurity, a semantic shift; other steps in the development of the future, he argues, are well-understood instances of sound change or analogy.
 - 12 A parent category covering not only prefixoids but also other categories like suffixoids.

TABLE 1 Five “tests for affixoids”, as proposed by Stevens (2005: 73)

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- a. “Affixoids [...] are [...] usually very productive”.
 - b. “Affixoids exist alongside a formally identical, and usually free, “parent” morph”.
 - c. “The meaning of the affixoid is more generalized and abstract than the formally identical parent”.
 - d. “There has been a shift of meaning in the relationship between the two parts of the word, so that the first, or other, component determines the basic meaning. That is, the syntactic relationship between the two morphemes is not like that a subordinating compound. The relationship between the parts of the word are [*sic*] also not like that in other compounds (copulative, exocentric, etc.)”.
 - e. “The affixoid must be in competition with or in complementary distribution with affixes”.
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These tests have been successfully applied in several recent studies on Greek (for example, Marinis 2020b, Marinis & Spetseri, 2019; Ralli 2020, 2018). However, since my goal here is to examine a distinctive subclass of affixoids, namely the prefixoids, I apply the tests given in Table 1 to prefixoids, and also propose and utilize some new ones (see the Criteria 1–10, below).

We define a prefixoid as an element whose morphological status changes as it moves from stem to prefix. Logically, we should expect the prefixoid to exhibit higher productivity than its precursor, confirming the prediction of Stevens’ test a for affixoids (Table 1). Nevertheless, how can we determine the theoretically expected productivity of prefixoids? According to Plag (1999), productivity is associated with the enhanced capability of an element to be more readily combined, facilitating the creation of new structures.

Thus, it is reasonable to expect that the new element will exhibit fewer categorical constraints and will combine with bases of more grammatical categories (Criterion 1).

Criterion 1

The prefixoid can be combined with bases belonging to more grammatical categories than its corresponding stem.

The idea that one element is more easily combinable than another should not be limited just to the lifting of categorical combinability constraints (see Criterion 1), but instead should be extended to the discriminating features of the

base. Since the features [+/-learnèd] and [+/-foreign] have been proposed as such features in the lexicon entry,¹³ we can introduce the following as Criterion 2:

Criterion 2

The prefixoid combines more easily with bases marked as [-learnèd] and/or [+foreign] than its corresponding stem.

The idea that the new element is more productive than its precursor type would be interesting to investigate at the semantic level as well, examining whether the new element extends combinability to words belonging to specific semantic domains (Criterion 3), without losing its ability to combine with other lexical items. This criterion, although not constituting a necessary condition for an element to be classified as a prefixoid, nevertheless can strengthen the case for the prefixoidal status of an element.

Criterion 3

Compared with its corresponding stem, a prefixoid may exhibit increased productivity in words belonging to particular semantic fields.¹⁴

In addition to its increase in productivity, an affixoid is expected to exist in parallel with the precursor type while continuing to exhibit exactly the same structure (see Stevens' test b, Table 1). However, in the particular case of prefixoids, the prediction of a "formally identical" type cannot apply because of the structural peculiarities of compounding in Greek, which always requires an *-o-* marker between the first and the second constituent (see a detailed discussion in Section 4). Moreover, we would expect the prefixoid to undergo phonological reduction, as functional elements like prefixes are, typically shorter than lexical stems.¹⁵ Thus, I am here going to consider 4 & 5 as criteria for prefixization:

Criterion 4

The emergence of a new element does not imply that the previous one is lost. The two elements coexist synchronically in the morphological system of the language.

13 See, for instance, Lieber (1980) in general, and for Greek, Ralli (2022).

14 Here, the relevant field is the set of pejorative items that can be used in swearing at someone; thus, for want of a better term, I use the feature "[+swearing]" as the label for such vocabulary.

15 See Zipf (1935) and Haspelmath (2008) on the way that high predictability and also high frequency of a sign can lead to its shorter phonological realization.

Criterion 5

Usually, the new element is phonologically differentiated from its predecessor.

In line with Stevens' test c for affixoids (Table 1), I consider an element to be a prefixoid based on Criterion 6:

Criterion 6

The prefixoid is semantically differentiated from its corresponding stem by its semantic expansion and its expression of a more abstract meaning.

Among the tests of affixoids catalogued by Stevens, test d (Table 1) predicts a change in the relationship between two-word components when one of them is an affixoid as opposed to a lexical stem. Applying this test to the case of prefixoids, it should be noted that in languages in which the Righthand Head Rule (RHR, Williams 1981) applies,¹⁶ it would be impossible for an element that develops into a prefix to be the structural head of the formation in which it participates (Criterion 7):

Criterion 7

Unlike a stem, a prefixoid can never be the structural head of the structures in which it participates.¹⁷

At the same time, it would be illogical to assume that an element that tends to develop into a prefix would carry the primary meaning (Criterion 8).

Criterion 8

A prefixoid can never be the semantic head of the structures in which it participates.

16 For Greek, Ralli (2022) notes that the Head is not always on the right edge, as suggested by Williams (1981). Depending on the morphological process (compounding, derivation, or inflection), the head may be located either on the left or on the right of the structure. Interestingly, while the RHR applies in SMG, it is not so consistent throughout Modern Greek dialects; for example, see the situation in Greko discussed by Marinis (2024c).

17 Criterion (7) proposed here for distinguishing prefixoids from stems is applicable to all languages presenting the Head on the right side of the structure.

Furthermore, due to the positioning of prefixes to the left of a structure, i.e., before the stem, it would be impossible to imagine a prefix occurring elsewhere in the structure (Criterion 9).

Criterion 9

A prefixoid is necessarily bound to the left of the morphological structure in which it occurs, whereas a stem may be found in (almost) any position within the structure in which it participates.

Finally, returning to the initial tests proposed by Stevens for affixoids in general, consider Stevens' test e (Table 1), which can be applied directly to prefixoids as such, without further parameterization (Criterion 10).

Criterion 10

The prefixoid must be in competition with or in complementary distribution with a prefix.

This study examines the words of Modern Greek that begin with *pale-* or *παλο-*. My data comes both from words listed in the dictionaries of Modern Greek and from two corpora of Standard Modern Greek: (a) The Greek Web Corpus (elTenTen; 2014), accessible through the platform Sketch Engine, and (b) the Corpus of Greek Texts (CGT; <http://sek.edu.gr>). The corpora are studied in order to verify the presence or absence of the studied structures, including vocabulary that is probably in use but not recorded in the dictionaries, as is likely to be the case with words belonging to obscene vocabulary. The presence or—most importantly—the absence of structures for each criterion specified in this chapter (see Criteria 1–10) is carefully documented. For example, the complete absence of words in which *pale-* is combined with obscene vocabulary is significant. Frequency of occurrence is not taken into account, since especially at the level of productivity, frequency may be influenced by temporal parameters that deprive us of an accurate synchronic picture of an ongoing change (see Plag, 1999; Ralli, 2022).

3 Comparing the data point by point

3.1 *Combinability with bases from more grammatical categories*

The constituent *pale-* combines with nominal stems (see, 6i–ii) but not with other grammatical categories, like adjectives, as in (6iii), adverbs, as in (6iv), or verbs, as in (6v).

- (6) i. *pale o anθropolo'jia*¹⁸
 old anthropology-NOUN
 'paleoanthropology'
- ii. *pale o vivliopo'lio*
 old bookstore-NOUN
 'secondhand bookstore'
- iii. **pale o 'citrinos*
 old yellow-ADJECTIVE
 'old fashioned yellow'
- iv. **pale o en'donos*
 old intensively-ADVERB
 'intensively the old way'
- v. **pale o po'lo*
 old sell-VERB
 'I sell the old way'

In contrast, the constituent *pa'lo-* can combine with nominal stems (see, e.g., 7i–ii) and also with adjectives (see, e.g., 7iii–iv).

- (7) i. *pa'lo ceros*
 weather-NOUN
 'bad weather'
- ii. *pa'lo ma'lakas*
 jerk-NOUN
 'huge jerk'
- iii. *pa'lo poni'ros*
 sly-ADJECTIVE
 'very cunning'

18 Historically, the word *paleoanθropolo'jia*, along with several others, was first created in Europe as a neoclassical compound and was later borrowed by Greek. However, since both the components and the entire structure are fully recognizable and analyzable to a Greek native speaker, (s)he readily perceives it as a typical Greek compound.

- iv. *πα'λο ι'λιθιος*
 stupid-ADJECTIVE
 'very stupid'

3.2 *Diacritic features of the base*

Another key difference between the two elements lies in the diacritic features of the words with which they can be combined. *pale-* combines with stems or words marked as [+learnèd], as illustrated in examples (8i) and (8ii), and in the examined corpora, *pale-* does not occur when combined with elements marked as [+foreign].

- (8) i. *paleopo'lio* 'antique shop'
 ii. *paleoyra'fia* 'palaeography'

Additionally, it is important to note that the [+learnèd] status of *pale-* allows it to combine with first (4i–iii) or second (8i–ii) constituents that are also [+learnèd]

By contrast, the element *παλο-* does not occur in combinations whose second constituent is marked as [+learnèd], but easily creates new words if combined with elements marked as [+foreign], as in examples (9i–ii).

- (9) i. *παλο'skuter* 'crappy scooter'
 ii. *παλο'jei* 'damn gay'

3.3 *Combinability with [+swearing] vocabulary*

παλο- has additionally extended its combinability to bases with swearing content, as in examples (10). In marked contrast, the element *pale-* does not occur as a constituent in formations whose second constituent has [+swearing] semantic content.

- (10) *παλομα'lakas* 'complete jerk'
παλοι'λιθιος 'total fool'
παλοkseftili'zmenos 'utterly jerky' (i.e. 'completely behaving like a jerk')

Crucially, the vast majority of these formations are neologisms.

3.4 *Co-existence with the precursor type*

Synchronically, *παλο-* coexists in the system alongside the element *pale-* from which it is diachronically derived. This coexistence is emphatically confirmed by cases in which the two elements are combined with the same constituent to create different words. Let us compare (iii) and (iii).

- (11) i. *paleoxristça'nos* 'early/old-fashioned Christian'
 ii. *παλοχριστça'nos* 'damn Christian'

In (11i), *pale-* carries the meaning of 'old', while in (11ii), *παλο-* brings a disparaging meaning to the formation.

3.5 *Phonological erosion*

The two elements being compared and examined undoubtedly both originate from the adjective *παλαιός paleos* 'old'. However, their present-day phonological realization is systematically differentiated. In comparing examples (12) and (13), note that in (12), the element *pale-* retains the original adjectival form from which it derives (*paleos*). The element has not undergone fusion and retains the hiatus, which, according to Giannoulopoulou (1999: 254), testifies to its ancient origin. At the same time, in (13), the first constituent (*παλο-*) shows the effects of phonological fusion of *-l- + -e-* to *-l-* and has also acquired a new final segment.¹⁹

- (12) *pale-o-po'lio* 'antique shop'

- (13) *παλο-μα'lakas* 'damn asshole'

3.6 *Semantic extension and/or shifting*

The element *pale-* in (14) means 'chronologically old, originating from or referring to a previous era'. For example, *paleoimerolo'jitis* (< *pale'os* 'old' + *imero'lojio* 'calendar') is a Christian who follows the Julian calendar, the traditional calendar of the Eastern Orthodox Church until 1923.

- (14) *paleoimerolo'jitis* 'old-calendarist'
paleokomuni'stis 'old-style communist'

In structures phonologically beginning with *παλο-*, the meaning has been either retained, as in (15i), or generalized and shifted, as in (15ii), to 'the unpleasant, the ugly, the qualitatively and morally degraded':²⁰

- (15) i. *παλοkor'θçotis* 'citizen of Old (Ancient) Corinth'
 ii. *παλοkomuni'stis* 'bloody communist'

¹⁹ See the discussion in Section 5, below.

²⁰ For a formal explanation of the nature of the element(s) in (15i) and (15ii), read the analysis proposed below, in Sections 4 and 5.

Clearly, the first component of the structure in (15) is derived from, or somehow related with, the first component of the structures in (14). The structural component in (15ii), however, has acquired a new meaning distinct from its precursor's. Moreover, the component *παλο-* can combine with words with derogatory content, as in (16), accentuating their disparaging meaning:

- (16) *παλοτα'lakas* < ma'lakas 'asshole'
παλο'vroma < 'vroma 'bitch'
παλοι'liθios < i'liθios 'stupid'

Note that the new meaning is not easily predictable from the meaning of the older element.²¹

3.7 *Category head*

In all the examples in my data, *παλο-* is never the grammatical head of the formations in which it participates. In contrast, *pale-* can easily be the grammatical head of the word in which it serves as a constituent. Actually, it is always the head when it is located in the right position of the morphological structure when the morphological process is derivation or compounding, and when it is located in the left position of the morphological structure, when the morphological process is inflection.²² For example, in (18), the formation *iperpale'os* is derived from the preposition *iper* and an adjective, *paleos*. The whole formation is an adjective because the adjective *paleos* is the grammatical head of the formation.

3.8 *Semantic head*

Comparing the two elements semantically, it is clear that the element *pale-* is the one that contributes the basic meaning to the formations in which it participates. See the examples (17) and (18) below.

21 Interestingly, the element *paleo-* never occurs in the corpora under consideration with the pejorative meaning of *παλο-*. However, in earlier phases of the historical development of the language, this was not the case. For instance, consider the following example from the late 13th to early 14th century, from Πουλολόγος 113, as it is cited by Kriaras (1967): *paleovraxoðar'menos* < *pale* + *o* + *vraxoðar'menos* 'who wished him to drown and be hit by the waves on the rocks', which offers textual testimony that *paleo-* formerly performed the role that *παλο-* now performs.

22 The behavior of this element confirms the more general proposal of Ralli (2022) regarding the differentiation of the position of the Head in Greek, depending on the particular morphological process applied (see footnote 16).

(17) *pam'baleos* 'very old'

(18) *iperpale'os* 'very old'

Unlike *pale-*, the element *παλο-* never contributes to the basic meaning of the formations in which it occurs. For example, (19), *παλομα'lakas* is not someone *παλο*²³ but someone *μα'lakas*:

(19) *παλομα'lakas* 'complete jerk'

3.9 *Position in the formation*

The elements under consideration also differ in their structural behavior, particularly in regard to their position to the right or left of the stem to which they attach. The element *pale-* may occur either as the first constituent, as in (20i–iii), or as the second constituent of the structures in which it participates, as in (20iv). However, in both (20i–iii) and (20iv), the meaning remains constant.

- (20) i. *paleoimerolo'jitis* 'old calendarist'
 ii. *paleopo'lio* 'antique shop'
 iii. *pam'baleos* 'extremely old'
 iv. *iperpale'os* 'extremely old'

- (21) i. *παλοji'neka* 'slut'
 ii. *πα'λοspito* 'bad house'

In contrast, the element *παλο-* differs from *pale-* in regard to the criterion under consideration. In particular, *παλο-* is always on the left of the structures in which it participates, as in (21i–ii), and never on the right. While *pale-* may occur either on the right or left, *παλο-* is obligatorily bound to the left of the structures in which it participates.

3.10 *In competition with a prefix*

The meaning of *παλο*—especially when it is combined with vocabulary marked as [+swearing]—is often expressed by other elements in the prefix category,

23 As a prefixoid, the constituent *παλο-* does not actually carry a purely lexical meaning. Combined with bases with derogatory content, the constituent *παλο-* exacerbates the negative meaning of the base. For this reason, the description of this element's meaning may appear to be somewhat inconsistent throughout the cited examples herein.

such as *kata-* or the Turkish-originated *kara-*. Interestingly, in examples (22i–iii), the meaning remains constant.

- (22) i. *paλoma'lakas* 'complete jerk'
 ii. *katama'lakas* 'complete jerk'
 iii. *karama'lakas* 'complete jerk'

4 Two bodies, one soul. Or ... not?

From the analysis of the data made in Section 3, it becomes clear that *pale-* and *paλo-* should be catalogued in the Lexicon as two separate morphemes. According to the analysis proposed here, the element *pale-* has retained the status of a stem, while the element *paλo-* has become a prefixoid. Supporting this analysis are all the criteria for prefixation set out in Section 2 and examined in the data presented in Section 3.

Significantly, in contra-distinction to *pale-*, *paλo-*:

1. Can be combined with bases from more grammatical categories—nouns and adjectives—unlike *pale-* which combines only with nouns.
2. Is easily combinable with bases marked with the diacritic feature [+foreign].
3. Is easily combinable with bases marked as [+swearing].
4. Over time, exhibits a semantic extension and/or shift from the precursor type (*pale-*). In particular, while *pale-* has retained the meaning of 'old', *paλo-* has a reduced lexical meaning and usually assigns a derogatory value to the element with which it is combined or, when combined with swearing vocabulary, accentuates the already-disparaging content.
5. Co-exists in the language alongside the precursor (*pale-*), often occurring in structures with the same second constituent, as in (6).
6. Has been phonologically altered in relation to the precursor type, as it has undergone fusion.
7. Cannot be the (grammatical) head of the formation it participates in.
8. Is never the semantic head of the formation in which it participates; the primary meaning of the new formation is always derived from another element of the formation in question and never from *paλo-*.
9. Is positionally bound, as it is always placed on the left edge of the formation in which it participates.
10. Can be in competition with prefixes like *para-*.

The mapping of the above data in Table 2 makes it clear that the two elements, *pale-* and *paλo-*, exhibit opposition in their attribute distribution for all the criteria proposed and considered here:

TABLE 2 Comparative analysis of *pale-* and *παλω-* based on the ten proposed criteria

Criteria examined	<i>pale-</i>	<i>παλω-</i>
1. Increased productivity in terms of grammatical category of the base	–	+
2. Increased productivity in terms of the diacritic features of the base	–	+
3. Increased productivity in terms of combinability with bases marked as [-learnèd, +swearing]	–	+
4. Co-existence with the precursor type	–	+
5. Phonological erosion	–	+
6. Semantic extension and/or shift	–	+
7. Inability to be the grammatical/categorical head of the formation	–	+
8. Inability to be the semantic head of the formation	–	+
9. Mandatory binding to the left of the formation	–	+
10. In competition with (a) prefix(es)	–	+

It should be noted that the element *pale-* sometimes may occur with phonological fusion, as *παλ-*, usually in predictable phonologically contexts. In contrast, the element *παλω-*, which has the status of a prefixoid, can never be realized as *pale-*.

Finally, it should be noted that the morpheme *pale-*, when participating in the first constituent of compound words, according to the Greek compound structural scheme (see Ralli 2013), is always followed by the compositional marker *-o-*. In the prefixoids, this compositional marker was reanalyzed as part of the first constituent of the structure,²⁴ as schematically depicted in (23):

(23)	1st constituent	2nd constituent	Morphological procedure
i:	<i>pale-</i>	<i>-o-</i> stem/word	Compounding
ii:	<i>παλ-</i>	<i>-o-</i> stem/word	Compounding
iii:	<i>παλω-</i>	stem/word	Derivation

24 To suppose that *-o-* here remains morphologically analyzable would mistakenly imply that it functions as an indicator of composition, and that—by extension—the preceding constituent, *παλ*, is a stem (for the schemes of compounding in Greek, see Ralli 2013). Such an analysis would require the existence of structures in which *παλ* occurs as a second constituent having the meaning of *παλω-*, of which there are none.

TABLE 3 The morphological status of *pale-*, *paλ-*, and *paλo-*

Entries in the lexicon	<i>pale-</i>	<i>paλo-</i>
Allomorphs	<i>pale~ paλ</i> ²⁵ (without allomorphs)	
Meaning	'old'	It bestows or intensifies a negative connotation for the second constituent
Morphological status	stem	prefixoid

In (23i–ii), the structure of the element *pale-*, which may occur with fusion,²⁶ (23ii), or without (23i), is schematically depicted. *pale-* is always a stem. When it participates in structures followed by another stem or word, the compositional marker *-o-* is always present. In contrast, in (23iii), the element *paλo-* is not a lexical stem and so does not participate in compounds; it functions as a prefixoid when it participates in morphological processes in which a stem or a word follows it. In this context, *-o-* is part of the *paλo-* morpheme, and it is no longer analyzable as a marker of composition. The morphological status and the relationship among the three elements catalogued in (23) are shown schematically in Table 3.

5 Conclusions

I hold that synchronically there are two discrete morphological elements related to the adjective *paleos* 'old'. However, in stark contrast to the analysis of Giannouloupoulou (1999), according to which the element *paλo-* is synchronically a stem (1993: 164), while the element *paleo-*²⁷ is a “confix” (1999: 139, 164) belonging to “the intermediate zones between compounding and derivation” (1999: 13), I propose precisely the opposite status for the two elements. The elements under consideration (*pale-*, *paλo-*) have been examined based on the ten criteria set forth in Section 2. The oppositional distribution of the values according to all the criteria examined clearly demonstrates that *pale-* and *paλo-*

25 The allomorphs are in complementary distribution regarding the distinctive feature [+/-learnèd] of the base, *pale-* being [+learnèd] and *paλ-* [-learnèd].

26 This distribution is not uniform across all Modern Greek dialects. For example, as Marinis (2024c) notes, in the Greek of South Italy, *paλ-* does not even appear.

27 In Section 1, I argue that this element's form is *pale*, and not *paleo*, and in Section 4, I show how its allomorphs are distributed.

constitute two distinct entries in the Lexicon; *pale-* is a stem, but *παλο-* is a prefixoid. However, it must be noted that meeting all ten criteria should not be considered necessary for an element to be characterized as a prefixoid. However, through the analysis presented here, it does become clear that the critical element in establishing *παλο-* as a prefixoid is how much more productive it is than its precursor.

In many languages having word-based morphology, prefixization can be seen to conform to Meillet's (1912) definition of grammaticalization; prefixoids move from word status to nonword status. However, I would like to suggest that for Greek, a language with stem-based morphology (see Ralli, 2022), prefixization accords more closely with Kuryłowicz's (1965; see Section 2) definition of grammaticalization, with prefixoids evolving from stems, which are already more grammatical than words, and tending towards prefix status. Thus, we should perhaps consider whether prefixoids for stem-based languages do indeed fall into the broader category of morphologization. This term, proposed by Joseph (2003), describes elements that start as free-standing items and eventually become bound morphemes. However, prefixoids in Greek seem to start as stems and end up as morphemes bound to the left of a morphological construction. In other words, they originate in morphology and remain within morphology. I suggest that this characteristic differentiates prefixization in Greek from the same process in word-based languages, such as English.

Undoubtedly, prefixes present a fascinating case study of the effects of diachrony on synchrony. They represent a great opportunity to observe an ongoing linguistic change, for which the endpoint—if any—can never be known. However, as an intermediate category between stems and prefixes, prefixoids offer a first-rate chance to explore the nature of these opposing categories along the morphological continuum and to determine their properties more precisely.

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